

DEVELOPING A COMPREHENSIVE ALUMNI-STUDENT INTERACTION PLATFORM

ENHANCING MENTORSHIP, STRESS MANAGEMENT, AND SKILL EXCHANGE FOR THE TECHNICAL EDUCATION DEPARTMENT

DR. S. AARTHI
ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR
HEAD, DEPARTMENT OF CSE
MEENAKSHI SUNDARARAJAN
ENGINEERING COLLEGE
CHENNAI , INDIA

VEDHA SREE G
MEENAKSHI SUNDARARAJAN
ENGINEERING COLLEGE
DEPT : CSE
CHENNAI , INDIA

YAZHINI PARVATHAM A
MEENAKSHI SUNDARARAJAN
ENGINEERING COLLEGE
DEPT : CSE
CHENNAI , INDIA

GNANALAKSHMI R
MEENAKSHI SUNDARARAJAN
ENGINEERING COLLEGE
DEPT : CSE
CHENNAI , INDIA

GEETHU S.S
MEENAKSHI SUNDARARAJAN
ENGINEERING COLLEGE
DEPT : CSE
CHENNAI , INDIA

JAYASHREE K J
MEENAKSHI SUNDARARAJAN
ENGINEERING COLLEGE
DEPT : CSE
CHENNAI , INDIA

ABINAYA S
MEENAKSHI SUNDARARAJAN
ENGINEERING COLLEGE
DEPT : CSE
CHENNAI , INDIA

skills and access exclusive content based on an activity-driven ranking system (Silver, Gold, Platinum). This paper discusses the platform's design, its functionality, and its impact on student well-being, career readiness, and alumni engagement.

Keywords — Alumni Mentorship, Student Stress Management, Skill Exchange, Personalized Guidance, Mental Health, Career Development, Blockchain Security, Artificial Intelligence

Abstract— In an era of intense academic pressure and career uncertainty, students face challenges in their studies, mental health, and future career planning. Alumni, with their real-world experience, are in a unique position to provide guidance and mentorship to students. This research paper presents a novel Alumni-Student Interaction Platform developed for the Technical Education Department, Government of Rajasthan. The platform is designed to address key issues, such as academic stress, career uncertainty, and the lack of a structured alumni engagement system. The platform incorporates real-time data analytics to offer personalized mentorship based on students' stress levels, academic performance, and mental health indicators. An additional skill exchange feature is integrated into the platform, enabling students and alumni to share

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's educational landscape, students often struggle not only with academic pressure but also with the overwhelming uncertainty about their future careers. Many students lack the proper guidance and mentorship necessary to navigate these challenges. Alumni, who have already overcome these struggles and succeeded in their respective fields, are ideally positioned to provide the needed mentorship, guidance, and real-world insights. However, a centralized, structured platform that connects students with alumni is often missing.

This research introduces a Comprehensive Alumni-Student Interaction Platform, designed to bridge this gap by connecting students with alumni for mentorship and guidance. In addition to this, the platform integrates a skill exchange feature that facilitates knowledge sharing between alumni and students, creating a dynamic and

collaborative learning environment. The platform's key feature is its use of real-time data to assess student stress levels and academic performance, enabling alumni to provide personalized support and career advice. The activity-driven skill exchange system categorizes participants into Silver, Gold, and Platinum tiers based on their engagement and skill-sharing activities, allowing access to different levels of content.

II. CURRENT CHALLENGES IN ALUMNI-STUDENT ENGAGEMENT

A. LACK OF CENTRALIZED SYSTEMS:

Many institutions lack a centralized platform to track alumni and facilitate structured alumni-student interactions.

B. FRAGMENTED MENTORSHIP OPPORTUNITIES:

Students are often left to seek guidance from alumni informally, leading to unstructured and inconsistent mentorship experiences.

C. RISING MENTAL HEALTH CONCERNS:

With increasing academic pressures, students face heightened levels of anxiety, depression, and stress, which are rarely addressed through alumni engagement platforms.

D. SKILL GAP:

Both students and alumni possess valuable skills that can be mutually beneficial, but there is no structured system for sharing and exchanging these skills.

E. LIMITED CAREER GUIDANCE:

Career counseling and real-world industry insights are often not integrated into alumni-student platforms, leaving students with inadequate preparation for the job market.

III. PROPOSED PLATFORM OVERVIEW

The platform is built around two core functionalities:

Personalized Alumni Mentorship through Data-Driven Insights: The platform leverages data such as students' academic performance, mental health status, stress levels,

and career aspirations to match students with relevant alumni who can provide tailored guidance.

Skill Exchange System: A tiered skill exchange feature allows students and alumni to share knowledge and skills, categorized into Silver, Gold, and Platinum levels based on their activity and contributions.

IV. PLATFORM FEATURES

4.1 Personalized Mentorship Based on Student Stress and Career Concerns

A unique feature of the platform is its ability to collect and analyze real-time data related to student stress, mental health, academic performance, and career concerns. The platform uses this data to update interconnected visual graphs in real time, offering insights such as:

Stress Level vs. Anxiety: Highlighting the correlation between students' stress and their anxiety levels.

Sleep Quality vs. Depression: Visualizing how poor sleep quality increases the likelihood of depression among students.

Career Concerns vs. Alumni-Student Engagement: Illustrating how students' anxiety about their future careers affects their engagement with alumni mentors.

By clicking on any of these data points, the system updates other relevant graphs to reveal deeper insights, such as:

How poor mental health impacts academic performance.

How stress manifests through physical symptoms, such as headaches or high blood pressure.

How alumni engagement can improve student well-being by addressing career concerns and providing emotional support.

4.2 Skill Exchange System

The Skill Exchange Platform introduces an innovative system for sharing and learning skills between students and alumni. Key components include:

Activity View and Share: Students and alumni can post and share skills they possess, categorized into different fields such as technology, management, and soft skills.

Ranking System (Silver, Gold, Platinum): Based on engagement and contributions, users are categorized into three levels:

Silver Tier: Basic access to shared skills and resources.

Gold Tier: Access to advanced content, including mentorship programs and career-oriented webinars.

Platinum Tier: Exclusive access to high-level content, one-on-one alumni mentorship, and personalized career guidance.

This tiered system motivates active participation and creates a sense of community where users are encouraged to engage, share, and learn from one another.

V. ADVANCED TECHNOLOGIES DRIVING THE PLATFORM

To ensure a seamless, secure, and personalized experience, the platform is powered by advanced technologies:

Artificial Intelligence (AI):

AI algorithms are used to recommend mentors based on student profiles, career goals, and academic data. AI also helps match students with the most relevant skill-sharing opportunities.

Machine Learning (ML):

ML models analyze patterns in student data to predict future stress levels, academic performance, and career needs, allowing alumni to provide proactive guidance.

Natural Language Processing (NLP):

NLP filters out harmful or inappropriate content from discussions and ensures a healthy, supportive environment.

Blockchain Security:

Blockchain ensures secure, tamper-proof records of alumni and student profiles, protecting data integrity and authenticity.

VI. IMPACT ON STUDENT WELL-BEING AND CAREER DEVELOPMENT

The platform aims to make a profound impact on students' academic success, mental health, and career preparedness by:

Reducing Stress and Anxiety: Personalized alumni guidance, based on real-time data, helps students manage academic stress and future career concerns more effectively.

Improving Academic Performance: Students receive timely advice on study habits, exam preparation, and skill-building, directly impacting their academic success.

Career Guidance: The platform provides structured mentorship that helps students make informed career decisions and enhances their preparedness for the job market.

Fostering Lifelong Connections: The platform nurtures ongoing alumni-student relationships, creating a professional network that extends beyond graduation.

VII. CONCLUSION

The proposed Alumni-Student Interaction Platform provides an innovative solution to the current challenges faced in alumni-student engagement. By utilizing data-driven insights and integrating a unique skill exchange system, the platform creates a holistic approach to mentorship and skill development. The addition of AI, ML, NLP, and Blockchain technologies ensures that the platform is not only personalized but also secure and efficient. This platform has the potential to transform alumni-student interactions, leading to improved student well-being, academic success, and career development.

Future work will focus on expanding the platform's capabilities, such as incorporating real-time feedback mechanisms and additional interactive features, to enhance the overall user experience.

References

- Goel, V., Gupta, M., & Agarwal, P. (2020). Mentorship platforms in education: Current trends and future challenges. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 45(2), 89-104.
- Smith, R., & Evans, J. (2019). Stress management in higher education: The role of mentors. *International Journal of Mental Health*, 56(4), 321-335.
- Patel, K., & Desai, R. (2021). Machine learning in personalized education: Applications and ethics. *AI & Society*, 23(1), 45-61.
- Thompson, L. (2019). Skill-based learning and its impact on career readiness: A case study. *Journal of Career Development*, 28(3), 174-191.

Zubair, F., & Anderson, T. (2020). Blockchain and its role in educational data security. *Journal of Information Security*, 12(1), 1-15.

Ahmed, S., & Khan, A. (2018). Artificial Intelligence in Education: Implications and challenges. *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 61(2), 67-75.

National Institute of Mental Health (2021). Anxiety and depression statistics in college students. Retrieved from <https://www.nimh.nih.gov>.

Technical Education Department, Government of Rajasthan (2024). Alumni-Student Interaction Initiative.